

Investigation of Lipid Profiles and Lipid Peroxidation in Patients with Type 2 Diabetes

Hanachi. P

*Women Research Centre, Biomedical Department
Alzahra University Tehran- Iran
E-mail: hanachi_wrc@yahoo.com
Tel: +98-9125426316; Fax: +9821-77498112*

Rashid Haydari Moghadam

Ilam Medical Science University Iran

Latiffah A.L

*Department of Community Health, Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences
University Putra Malaysia*

Abstract

The aim of this study was to investigate the lipid peroxidation of plasma as a marker of oxidant-induced protein damage the effects of oxygen radicals on glycated-hemoglobin and to find out the relationship between the increase level of Malondialdehyde (MDA) on HbA1C, lipid profiles and FBS (Fasting Blood Sugar) in patients with type 2 diabetes. This randomized study included 200 individuals, 100 cases had history of diabetic for at least 3 years (file in Isfahan hospital, Diabetic Center of Medical Sciences University) and 100 cases as the control group without history of diabetes. In both groups, level of MDA, FBS, lipid profiles and HbA1C were determined in fasting blood samples. Results showed that MDA level in diabetic patients was significantly ($p < 0.005$) higher ($0.9222 \pm 0.3 \mu\text{mol/L}$) than those in the control group ($0.7428 \pm 0.04 \mu\text{mol/L}$). The same was also true ($p < 0.05$) for the level of HbA1C ($9.387 \pm 2.4 \text{ mg/dl}$ in diabetic patients and $7.356 \pm 1.0 \text{ mg/dl}$ in the control group) and the FBS ($163.31 \pm 56 \text{ mg/dl}$ in patient group and 85.740 ± 10.1 in the control group). Furthermore, the concentration of, LDL significantly was higher ($p < 0.05$) and the HDL level were significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) in case group as compared to control group. The increased plasma lipid peroxidation and decreased plasma HDL that we observed in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus indicated that these may predispose to the development of cardiovascular complications.

Keywords: Malondialdehyde, FBS, HbA1C, Lipid peroxidation

Introduction

Diabetes mellitus is a major source of morbidity in developed countries. Morbidity and mortality are increased in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus compared with the general population, particularly with respect to coronary artery disease. One possible explanation for this is that oxidative stress may be a contributory factor. Free radicals are highly reactive molecules generated by biochemical redox

reactions that occur as a part of normal cell metabolism (Kohen *et al.*, 1996). These unstable species may cause oxidative damage to DNA, carbohydrate, proteins and lipids that are normally counteracted by protective antioxidants. Excessive free radical production or low antioxidant level leads to oxidation of cellular lipids, proteins and nucleic acids, which results in fragmentation and cross-linking. This may ultimately lead to cell death with widespread pathological consequences (Baynes, 1991). The imbalance between protective antioxidants (antioxidant defense) and increased free radical production, leading to oxidative damage, is known as oxidative stress (Hanachi *et al.*, 2004). Oxidative stress is caused by a relative overload of oxidants, i.e., reactive oxygen species and the evidence suggests complications of diabetes partially is mediated by oxidative stress (Hayoz *et al.*, (1998)., Rosen *et al.*, 1998., Szaleczky *et al.*, 1999).

The reliance on a single blood glucose measurement, as recent prospective data have clearly established a link between a marker for chronic average glucose levels Hemoglobin A1c (HbA1C) and cardiovascular morbidity and mortality (Singer *et al.*, 1992).

In 30 to 40% of Diabetes Mellitus (DM) patients lipid disorders may be present. Increased levels of triglyceride-rich lipoproteins have been reported in diabetic patients and this atherogenic profile becomes more apparent. Oxidative stress can be measured by monitoring the changes in blood Malondialdehyde (MDA) which is a marker of lipid oxidation. Evidence suggest that oxidative damage is increased in diabetes (West, 2000). Some of studies have implied that Lipid peroxidation acts on fatty acid and begin to change the lipids structure (Murray, 1996). As a result of this peroxidation, substances such as MDA is produced which attacks the lysine amino acid in protein which results in proteolysis (Buege,1987). Oxidative stress arises because of excessive production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and impaired antioxidant defense mechanisms (Antoine *et al.*, 2002). It has been suggested that ROS induce membrane lipid peroxidation and that the toxicity of generated fatty acid peroxides are important causes of cells malfunction (Sanocka and Kurpisz 2004). The most widely used assay for lipid peroxidation involves the measurement of MDA - thiobarbituric acid (TBA) adducts due to its simplicity (Gomez *et al.*, 1998).

There are a few reports describing the differences in plasma lipid peroxidation, lipid profiles and HbA1C between patients with type 2 diabetes and control group. This study was designed to determine the changes of plasma lipid peroxidation, lipid profiles, FBS and HbA1C in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (at a diabetes center in Isfahan hospital) in comparison to controls.

Materials and Methods

Samples

200 individuals attending in Isfahan hospital, Diabetic Center of Medical Sciences University with mean age of 54 ± 7 were selected (include 66% males and 24% females). Samples were obtained, in a randomized fashion, from 100 patients with type 2 diabetes as well as 100 control subjects without diabetes attending the same center. Subjects were chosen from the patients referred to the Isfahan hospital, diabetic center of Medical Sciences University. The patients in the study had no evidence of vascular complications, including hypertension and coronary artery disease. Controls were defined as not having a major medical illness, no hospital admissions, no current medication, and a subjective perception of good health as determined by health questionnaire. None of the study subjects received any medication and trace element supplement in the previous 2-3 months. Blood samples were collected after an overnight fast (14 hours) in heparinized tubes.

Lipid Profiles Assay

Plasma was separated soon after fasting blood was taken, Cholesterol, LDL, HDL and triglycerides were measured by using the enzymatic method technique, spectrophotometer assays with using the Chem Enzyme, Co kit.

Malondialdehyde Measurement

The MDA concentration ($\mu\text{mol/lit}$) was determined by the thiobarbituric acid (TBA) assay according to the Kastner *et al*, (1997). To 0.5 ml plasma, 1 ml of trichloroacetic acid was added and the tube was left to stand for 10 min at room temperature. After centrifugation at 3500 RPM for 10 min, the supernatant was separated. Thereafter 0.5 ml supernatant were added to 0.5 ml thiobarbituric acid (TBA) and carried out in a boiling water bath for 30 min. After cooling in cold water, the resulting chromogen absorbance was determined at the wavelength of 532 nm.

Glycated Hemoglobin Measurement

Glycated Hemoglobin (A1c) was measured using the thiobarbituric acid colorimetric reaction (Parker *et al*, 1981). The colorimetric method with 2-thiobarbituric acid is based on the hydrolysis of the glycated proteins using oxalic acid at 100°C yielding 5-hydroxymethyl furfural (5-HMF) which reacts with thiobarbituric acid. The absorbance was measured at 443 nm. 5-HMF was used as a standard and glycation of hemoglobin.

Glucose Assay

The glucose assay was performed based on colorimetric enzyme method. In this method, glucose with effect of Glucose oxidase can be enzymatically oxidized to gluconic acid and hydrogen peroxide in the presence of peroxidase, the hydrogen peroxide reacts with 4-amino antipyrine (4- AAP) and N-ethyl-N-sulfopropyl-m-toluidine (TOPS) to form violet-colored quinoneimine, which has an absorbance peak at 520 nm Trinder 1969).

Statistical Analysis

All sample analyses were run in triplicate. The data was analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 12.0 using the Student's t-test. The comparison of the change in parameters between patient and control groups as the main outcome were made by ANOVA using the General Linear Model for repeated measures. In light of multiple comparisons, statistical significance will be assigned at $p < 0.05$ for all analysis.

Results

The results show that, the mean for age of control group was 54 ± 7 years, while 52 ± 6 years for type 2 diabetes mellitus patients (66 percent males and 24 percent females). The FBS (mg/dl) level in Case was 163.31 ± 56 and Control = 85.740 ± 10.1 ($p < 0.05$). The percentage of HbA1c in Case = 9.387 ± 2.4 and Control 7.356 ± 1.0 9. Subjects with type 2 diabetes mellitus had significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher fasting blood glucose, and HbA1c levels and significantly lower HDL cholesterol than control subjects. There were a significant relationship between the concentration of HbA1c and FBS in case and control groups ($P < 0.05$). The FBS and HbA1c were found to be significantly higher $p < 0.05$ in diabetic patient as compared to control group (Figure 1 and 2). The concentration of, LDL significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher and HDL level were significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower in diabetic patient as compared to control group ($p < 0.05$). The cholesterol and triglycerides concentration substantially increased but had no significant difference in patient compared with control groups (figure.3). In comparison, the HDL concentration was significantly ($p < 0.05$) decreased in patient compared with control group. The type 2 diabetes patients group displayed higher plasma concentration of LDL ($p < 0.05$) compared with control group (figure.3). The MDA concentration increased significantly ($p < 0.05$) in patient compared with control groups by 0.922 ± 0.3 and 0.742 ± 0.04 respectively (Figure. 4).

There was not relation between MDA level and other factors in both groups. In fact may MDA had no effect on the level of FBS and HbA1C level in case and control group.

Figure 1: Serum FBS concentration in control and NIDDM (type 2 diabetes) patient.

* Significant level was ($P < 0.05$). Data are mean \pm S.E.M.

Figure 2: Serum HbA1C % in control and NIDDM patient (type 2 diabetes)

* Significant level was ($P < 0.05$). Data are mean \pm S.E.M.

Figure 3: Serum lipid profiles in control and NIDDM patient (type 2 diabetes).

* Significant level was set at level ($P < 0.05$). Data are mean \pm S.E.M.

Figure 4: Serum MDA concentration in control and NIDDM patient (type 2 diabetes).

* Significant level was ($P < 0.05$). Data are mean \pm S.E.M.

Discussion

Several studies have reported an increased susceptibility to lipid peroxidation in patients with diabetes mellitus (Gallou *et al.*, 1993). However, the influence of blood glucose control, lipid characteristics, and type of diabetes on the susceptibility of LDL to oxidation remains controversial (Lyons, 1991). In this cross sectioned study, we have evaluated serum MDA levels and its relationship with other biochemical finding i.e. FBS, lipid profiles and HbA1C%. Our study confers with study conducted by Tan *et al.*, (2001) that found glucose was higher in NIDDM patient. Lipid peroxidation products (MDA levels) were higher in patients with uncontrolled type 2 diabetes compared to patients with controlled type 2 diabetes (Jain *et al.*, 1999). Furthermore, our study confers with study conducted by Maxwell *et al.* (1997) that shows, oxidative stress may be increased in diabetes due to exposure to prolonged

periods of hyperglycemia, which causes non-enzymatic glycation of plasma proteins (binding of glucose to protein molecules). In this study higher level of MDA was denoted in diabetic patients than in control groups. A similar finding was reported by Dierckx *et al*, (2003). The serum triglycerides levels had no significant difference between two groups. This result did not agree with the finding by Tan *et al*,(2001). The results from this study contradicted the finding by Hiroshi *et al*, (1997) that demonstrated diabetes had higher mean LDL and lower serum HDL than the normal subjects. We were unable to demonstrate the correlation between glucose and lag time of LDL oxidation separately in any of the groups, possibly because of clustering of glucose data within each group. Person's correlation analysis was done to determine the association between MDA and other biochemical parameters, However it was not significant. Supplementation with dietary free radical scavengers such as vitamins E and C have a potential role in boosting antioxidant-related defenses and maybe important in patients with diabetes (Dieber, 1991; Porkkala, 1996).

Results from this study have shown that patients with diabetics have higher MDA levels in their blood serum and that glycated hemoglobin and serum glucose level in these patients are related. The interpretation of the data could be biased by such confounding factors, particularly because plasma lipid peroxidation seems to be linked to lipid concentrations and the degree of hyperglycemia. In conclusion, we found that oxidative susceptibility *in vivo* is increased in subjects with type 2 diabetes compared with non-diabetic subject. The increased plasma lipid peroxidation and decreased plasma HDL that we observed in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus may suggest that predispose to the development of cardiovascular complications. Supplementation with dietary free radical scavengers such as vitamins E and C have a potential role in boosting antioxidant-related defenses and maybe important in patients with diabetes. We propose that diabetic patients may have elevated requirement for antioxidants.

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